

Erasmus 2024 spring semester projects*

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Abstract

In this collection of papers we conclude the work being done while on Erasmus stay at Izmir University of Economics. First paper includes the simulation of non-Keplerian orbits, temperature distribution based on Gauss-Seidel method and calculation of error convergence for both problems. The second paper demonstrates a step-by-step setup and overview of the TinyGS ground station and the data acquisition augmented by time dependant visualisation made in OpenMCT of current and past telemetry for a specific satellite.

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Non-Keplerian orbit simulation and temperature distribution analysis using Xcos, OpenModelica and Python

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider the simulation of non-Keplerian orbits via Xcos and Modelica, temperature distribution based on Gauss-Seidel method in Modelica and Python in a two-dimensional (2D) example, calculation of error convergence for both problem of orbits and the two-dimensional problem of temperature distribution.

1 Introduction

Orbits of objects that are influenced by external factors are inherently difficult to predict. Solar radiation pressure area acts as a reflector for solar energy and as an air brake for the atmosphere in low earth orbit.

Thermal analysis in 2D is an example made to demonstrate the difference that is created by sources with constant values and that the potential exists between them. Two methods of calculating with the Gauss-Seidel method are discussed, one made in Modelica language employing matrix multiplication to achieve averaging over neighbors and the second one in Python where calculation is done on randomly selected cells for a specific number of calculation loops.

Numerical methods done in multiple simulation tools and with different methods can vary, the problem is that this deviation is not known and how this deviation changes. In this project, the use of multiple tools acts as a guarantee that different tools with different methods tend to similar results, which can be the basis for conclusions - how did the inclusion of solar logic change the orbit and how comparable are two methods to calculate the temperature distribution in an area.

2 Orbit modelling methodologies

2.1 Tools

Scilab Xcos is a block diagram simulation tool capable of acausal calculations. Its blocks [1] were recreated in Modelica language to run in OpenModelica software [2]. Later on, after simulations were completed, the results were transferred to either Python for further post-processing or to Gnuplot and displayed in a chart. The integration method used to calculate the orbits within both of the tools was Rungekutta at a tolerance of 10^{-6} with varied simulation intervals.

2.2 Eclipse cutoff equations

Equations used to determine whether the orbiting spacecraft is in total or partial eclipse.

Figure 1: Earth-Sun diagram denoting the partial eclipse with dotted line behind earth and total eclipse with solid line behind Earth \oplus with respect to the Sun \odot

d - 1 au, Distance of Earth to Sun

r - Radius of the Earth \oplus

R - Radius of the Sun \odot

The equation to calculate the total eclipse cutoff point

$$y = -\frac{d(1 - \frac{1}{\frac{r}{R} + 1})\sqrt{1 - (\frac{r^2 + r}{d})^2}}{r}x + \frac{d}{\frac{r}{R} + 1} \quad (1)$$

The equation to calculate the partial eclipse cutoff point

$$y = \frac{d}{(r - R)\sqrt{1 - (\frac{R - r}{d})^2}}x - \frac{dR}{r - R} \quad (2)$$

3 Temperature distribution methodologies

3.1 Tools

The simulations of heat equations were conducted in Modelica language to run in OpenModelica software and Python. The two different approaches were in two different programs. The averaging of closest neighboring values was done separately through the addition of shifted matrixes (Equation 6) and averaging over random rows and columns (Figure 2) as two distinct ways.

3.2 Gauss-Seidel

Poisson's equation [3](p. 463), which is the same for voltage and temperature can be used to approximate temperature potential in a given area or a volume. It helps to model the temperature distribution through a given medium.

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 V = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Thermal radiation T is proportional to voltage V.

$$T \propto V \quad (4)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \vec{\nabla}^2 V = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} = 0 \\ T \propto V \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow \vec{\nabla}^2 T = 0 \quad (5)$$

These equations can be represented by multiple passes of averaging over neighboring cells. The selection of these cells can be based on a predefined walk or a random selection. Both of these methodologies have potential problems. A walk can influence the direction in which the heat distributes the fastest. Random method can take much more time to realize, because of an initial state where most of the cells are of similarly low value which would have been averaged over without significantly changing the result.

3.3 Initial state

The initial state of the matrix $I_{20,32}$ shows the outermost edges being set to 0, two horizontal lines being set to 100, the rest of the values set to 1. Where values that are set to either 0 or 100 are not changed throughout the simulation and denote the lowest and highest temperature respectively.

The below methods both use the $I_{20,32}$ matrix as a starting point with the rules set above. The number of recursions in a simulation is represented by k for Modelica - matrix addition, $k \times 640$ for Python - random walk. The value 640 corresponds to a number of possible positions that an averaging can occur in a random walk.

$$I_{20,32} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 100_{7,11} & \dots & 100_{7,22} & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 100_{14,11} & \dots & 100_{14,22} & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

4 Orbit calculation results

Figure 3: Combined orbit with and without full and partial eclipse

(a) overview

(b) closeup view

Figure 4: Orbit of full and partial eclipse

The data in this section was composed by several tools working in tandem - Scilab Xcos and OpenModelica. The spacecraft used in the simulation has an exaggerated solar radiation pressure area, 6000 m^2 from original of 32 m^2 [6] and responds to its position with respect to perihelion and aphelion by minimizing solar radiation pressure to 0 m^2 going towards the Sun and maximum 6000 m^2 going away from the sun excluding eclipses. The orbit with partial, and total eclipse that the simulation time is $t = 2 \times 10^6$ seconds exhibits the procession of the apoapsis clockwise from the sun. In this simulation, it can also be seen that

the perihelion gets smaller than the radius of the Earth (Figure 4), showing that the initial altitude was too small to support this orbit, a fact that was discussed in the paper by Spencer et al. [6] regardless of available radiation pressure area.

5 Temperature distribution results

Figure 5 and Figure 6 represent the results acquired from the simulations made in Modelica and Python.

Figure 5: Temperature distribution at $k = 25$

Figure 6: Temperature distribution at $k = 300$

It can be seen that temperature distribution differences between random averaging and matrix addition are more prominent at $k = 25$ but much less noticeable at $k = 300$. This is due to the fraction of the result that a simulation is responsible for. The higher the k becomes - the simulation's contribution gets decreasingly smaller.

6 Convergence Results

It was possible to calculate L2 norm error with this equation, which was modified from [7](p.17).

$$\|e\| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_0^N (f_{\Delta t_{i-1}} - f_{\Delta t_i})^2} \quad (8)$$

6.1 Orbit calculation

Using the output of the OpenModelica and Scilab Xcos simulations, ranging from $\Delta t = 0.01$ to $\Delta t = 0.15$ seconds of time interval it was possible to calculate the L2 norm error.

Figure 7: L2 norm error

The graph of a bigger scope couldn't be achieved because of a limitation in OpenModelica where the simulation interval is limited to less than one second.

The complete graph shows the relation of error in kilometers to delta time in seconds. The decrease in delta time is proportional to the decrease in measured error. This corresponds to the convergence of measured data in both simulation tools.

6.2 Temperature distribution calculation

Using the output of Modelica and Python from conducted simulations ranging from $k = 25$ to $k = 300$ it was possible to calculate the L2 norm error.

Figure 8: L2 norm error for temperature distribution

The graph shows that with the increase in k iterations for matrix addition, $k \times 640$ - iterations in a random walk, the corresponding error gets decreasingly smaller. At $k = 200$ and above the error value is approximate to $\|e\| \approx 6.9 \times 10^{-3}$ of error between the above methods.

7 Observations

The project researched simulations of non-Keplerian orbits and temperature distribution using Xcos, OpenModelica, and Python.

The partial eclipse has a small effect when the orbit of the spacecraft is low when time spent during partial eclipse is negligible. As the semi-major axis increases, the time spent in a partial eclipse compared to total eclipse increases. Both types of eclipses affect the final position of a spacecraft, they should be included to get a more realistic result (Figure 3). With full and partial eclipses included, the procession of apoapsis is observed (Figure 4 a).

With the increase in the number of simulation steps, there is a significant rise in calculations needed to arrive at a stable thermal system. Both methods exhibit a problem where calculations will be done even when the neighboring values are the same, wasting resources. Further development in statistical methods and weight systems can be used to negate it.

Results gathered from the simulations made in this project show that the models from both software tools converge on the same answer with a decrease in the simulation time step interval (Figure 7). The matrix addition and random walk saw a decrease in error with an increase in simulation steps. The decrease in error became less significant as k crossed 200 (Figure 8).

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Visualization and analysis of CubeSat data with TinyGS and OpenMCT

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Abstract

In this project we demonstrate a step-by-step setup and overview of the TinyGS ground station, a system responsible for connecting and distributing data from remote stations and the data acquisition augmented by time dependant visualisation made in OpenMCT of current and past telemetry for a specific satellite.

1 Introduction

Micro-satellites such as CubeSats, with technological advances in miniaturization are a cheaper alternative for research, educational institutions and the private sector compared to more traditional highly specialized made-to-order government and commercial satellites. With the proliferation of such, various communication projects were started. This project will show a step-by-step showcase of TinyGS CubeSat ground station receiver as well as a local setup of OpenMCT for satellite telemetry monitoring.

2 Communication standard

The frequency used for TinyGS communication with amateur CubeSat satellites or professional telemetry channels of commercial or state-owned satellites in low earth orbit is in hundreds of megahertz - 433MHz, 868MHz. This is dictated by the availability of COTS (Commercial Off The Shelf) components. One of the modulation techniques at these frequencies is known as LoRa and is used in this system, a low power, below noise level way of sending small amounts of data [1] between two links.

3 System topology

The TinyGS system enables efficient communication between a satellite equipped with a LoRa transmitter and ground-based components. Ground stations receive data transmitted by the satellite and forward it to the central TinyGS server infrastructure. This infrastructure manages and processes the incoming data, decoding the raw telemetry frames (JSON) from each station, merging them to reduce duplicates and making it accessible via TinyGS API endpoints. When the station receives an incomplete frame, the server can correctly assign it to a particular satellite, even if the data is illegible, making it a packet with a CRC error.

The OpenMCT server and its web API provide a platform for data visualization and control. Saving the historical data to a local database and serving it as needed to a web service client.

This topology enables web clients to use the whole network to gather telemetry data for each available satellite.

Figure 1: Network topology, based on [TinyGS_architecture.png](#)

4 Ground station setup

Figure 2: Exemplary ground station device "LILYGO T3 LoRa" in access point mode

4.1 Configuration page

Setup of the ground station was made using software version 0.05, future changes may influence how the station may need to be configured.

After powering up the base station for the first time the prompt to connect to the station's access point will be shown and has to be connected to, to set up the base station. After selecting the configuration page, the settings such as station name and station password have to be changed for later reference.

The station name represents this particular station in the whole network. This name has to be concise and not include any special characters, it will be available to see on the network website.

The working location of the ground station with an approximation to three decimal places has to be included for the calculation of the selected listened satellite.

System configuration

GroundStation Name (will be seen on the map)

Password for this dashboard (user is **admin**)

WiFi SSID

WiFi password

Latitude (3 decimals, will be public)

Longitude (3 decimals, will be public)

Time Zone

Europe/Warsaw

MQTT credentials (get them [here](#))

Server address

Server Port

MQTT Username

MQTT Password

Board config

Board type

433 Mhz TTGO LoRA 32 v2

OLED Bright

Enable TX (HAM licence/ no preamp)

Allow Automatic Tuning

Allow sending telemetry to third party

Test mode

Automatic Firmware Update

Advanced Config (do not modify unless you know what you are doing)

Board Template (requires manual restart)

Modem startup

Advanced parameters

Apply

[Firmware update](#)

Firmware config version '0.05'

Figure 3: Local website setup view of a ground station

4.2 Final setup

To obtain the MQTT username and password as of June 2024, [Telegram TinyGS server](#) and the @tinygs_personal_bot has to be added to a contact list in the Telegram and messaged “/mqtt”. Any further status updates and changes can be done through this bot, the list of such is available by sending “/start”.

If in the residing country, the transmission of radio waves on ISM bands is forbidden to the unauthorized person, the option “Enable TX” has to be set to “off”. To save the current state, click “Apply”.

Additional setup steps for advanced station setup are available on the station configuration website [\[2\]](#).

(a) Access point mode

(b) Empty data for satellite

(c) Location of satellite

Figure 4: Station set up modes

(a) Name of ground station

(b) IP address of station

(c) Data of listened satellite

(d) Estimated location of satellite

Figure 5: Station standby mode

After the above settings are set the station will connect through the provided Wi-Fi to the MQTT server and obtain the location of the satellite that it is assigned to listen to (Figure 4). During normal operation, the screen will show current status (Figure 5).

Additional resources are available on the TinyGS website [3] or on the documentation GitHub page [4].

(a) Izmir, Turkey area

(b) Some LEO sats available by TinyGS

Figure 6: TinyGS website excerpt

Figure 7: Antenna setup being tested in Izmir University of Economics

5 OpenMCT setup

OpenMCT is a widely used open-source monitoring program in high-performance, mission-critical and hobby-build projects. Used by professionals and enthusiasts alike, it is renowned for its customizability [5].

Figure 8: Data gathered from CSTP-1.2 CubeSat displayed in OpenMCT

Figure 9: Layout displaying data from Tianqi-7 satellite in OpenMCT

Using the overview of the OpenMCT [6] and an official tutorial configuration [7] files, the Docker image including all necessary elements was created [8]. In the current configuration, OpenMCT (Figure 6) is used as a telemetry reader for packets stored as a buffer in a simple local database (SQLite) that stores the last 10 minutes worth of packets coming from TinyGS servers for a given satellite to later be handled by web-socket connection. Packets that are displayed are offset in time by 10 minutes from real time measurement, which is reflected in the timeline. The data can be seen in as a time graph feed based on web sockets. Each view can be manipulated to suit individual needs (Figure 9).

6 Conclusions

With the use of TinyGS ground stations acting as a network feeding information to OpenMCT, the data from satellites can be visualized almost in real time. Storing historical information on satellites of interest can be beneficial for future examination and simulation with hardware in the loop.

As more satellites are available and the telemetry data includes more information on the status of a spacecraft the digital twin concept can be accomplished.

With the advent of civilian satellites made by Universities (CSTP-1.2) and private parties (LightSail-2) the open source networks of receivers and transmitters as well as visualizing systems become more important for telemetry and any other activities done onboard that need a connection with ground control.

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